

Synthesis of Coersivity and Magnetic Moment of Nanoparticle Sized Aluminium Substituted Copper Cobalt Ferrites

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Abstract:

The polycrystalline aluminium substituted nano-particle sized copper cobalt ferrite samples $Cu_xCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-2y}Al_{2y}O_4$ (where $x= 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0$; $y = 0.05, 0.15$ and 0.25) have been prepared by standard ceramic technique. Phase formation is investigated using X-ray diffraction, Infrared absorption technique and Scanning electron microscope technique. Magnetic properties of the samples are investigated by using Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) and Helmholtz's double coil apparatus. The lattice constants of the all samples are evaluated from x-ray diffraction data. A universal testing machine as well as Archimedes's method was applied for determining the physical properties of the samples. Ionic radii R_A and bond lengths (A-O) on both sites are found decreases with Al^{3+} and copper content. The Lattice constant 'a', physical density as well as X-ray density of samples goes on increasing with Al^{3+} and copper content. The ratio c/a is found increasing when addition of copper content and decreases with aluminum content. It means that Al^{3+} and copper acquire the tetragonal prolate type distortions on B site and hence (c/a) ratio increases and automatically crystal lattice turned from tetragonal spinel to cubic spinel. Addition of Al^{3+} replaces Fe^{3+} on A-site and hence magnetic moment per unit values decreases. Copper cobalt ferrite exhibits canting of spins of magnetic moments on B-site. The canting angle α_{yk} is found decreasing with Al^{3+} content in the host lattice.

Keywords: Polycrystalline, Standard Ceramic Technique, Magnetic Moment, Canting Angle

Introduction:

In a way, every material utilized today is a composite. Composite materials are a physical mixture of two or more compatible micro or macro constituent particles which differ in form and chemical composition and are essentially insoluble in each other. Composite materials are best suited for scientific applications which could not be achieved by any one component acting on its own properties. Ferrite / ferroelectric composites are termed as magneto electric (ME) composites due to the coupling between the electric and magnetic fields in the materials. The conversion of magnetic to electric fields in such ME composite originates from the elastic interaction between ferrite and ferroelectric

subsystems [1]. In the presence of the magnetic field, the magnetostriction in the ferrite phase gives rise to mechanical stresses that are transferred to the ferroelectric phase, resulting in electric polarization of the ferroelectric phase owing to its magneto electric effect. ME materials find applications as smart materials in actuators, sensors, magnetic probes, phase inverters, rectifiers, modulators, and transducers in solid state microelectronics and microwave devices [2,3].

Spinel ferrite nanoparticles are being intensively investigated in recent years because of their remarkable electrical and magnetic properties and wide practical applications in information storage system, ferro-fluid

technology, magnetocaloric refrigeration and medical diagnosis [4]. Among the spinels, mixed Zn ferrites and especially Ni–Zn ferrites are widely used in applications like transformer cores, chokes, coils, noise filters recording heads etc. [5]. While Ni–Zn ferrite possesses higher resistivity and saturation magnetization, cobalt ferrite possesses high cubic magneto crystalline anisotropy and hence high coercivity. The high coercivity is driven by large anisotropy of the cobalt ions due to its important spin orbit coupling. It is ferromagnetic with a Curie temperature (T_c) around 520°C, [6] and shows a relatively large magnetic hysteresis which distinguishes it from rest of the spinels. The synthesis of ultra fine magnetic particles has been extensively investigated in recent years because of their potential applications in high density magnetic recording and magnetic fluids [7]. Among the current methods for synthesis of mixed ferrite the combustion reaction method stands out as an alternative and highly promising method for the synthesis of these ferrites [8]. Magnetic properties measured at room temperature by vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) reveal an increase in saturation magnetization with increase in cobalt concentration [9].

Experimental:

The ferrites with general chemical formula $Cu_xCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-2y}Al_{2y}O_4$ (where $x = 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0$; $y = 0.05, 0.15$ and 0.25) were prepared by the standard ceramic technique using AR grade cobalt oxide, copper oxide, ferric oxide and aluminium oxide. The compositional weights of powders were mixed physically and blended in agate mortar in acetone medium. The final sintering process was carried at 1000°C for 48 hours. The slow cooled samples were heated at rate of 80°C per hour. The pellets and toroids

were formed by using respective steel die. A universal testing machine as well as Archimedes's method was applied for determining the physical properties of the samples. The formation of the cubic spinel structure of the samples prepared is confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis. Saturation magnetization of each was carried out using high-field hysteresis loop tracer and presented in fig.2. The saturation magnetization (σ_s), magnetic moment (n_B) were determined from the magnetization study and presented by graphs (Fig.3)

Results and Discussion:

The lattice constants 'a' and 'c' for all prepared samples are calculated by using prominent (311) XRD peak [10]. The calculated and observed values of inter planer distance (d) are found in good agreement with each other for all reflections. The particle size (D) for all the ferrite samples is calculated by Debye Scherer formula, ionic site radii (R_A, R_B) and ionic bond lengths (A-O, B-O) are calculated from the formulae given by Gadkari et.al [11]. From the calculations of lattice constants 'a' and 'c' for all the prepared ferrites; it is observed that $c > a$; tetragonality ratio (c/a) is found in the range of 1.03 to 1.07. This result is in good agreement with previous report [12-13].

Fig. 1 Characterisation of ferrite samples by XRD,IR, SEM

The infrared absorption spectra showing two distinct absorption band ν_1 due to tetrahedral (A) site interstitial voids near 600 cm^{-1} and other ν_2 due to octahedral (B) site interstitial voids near 400 cm^{-1} . Our results in this present communication are well supported by previous reports [14, 15].

The close inspection of all micrographs revealed that there is continuous grain growth with well defined grain boundaries formed. The present system shows multi domain behaviour. No exaggerated grain growth is observed in any

of this composition. The average grain size is found to decrease with increase in Al content in copper cobalt ferrite. However in the present system the grain growth shows generally a decreasing trend with aluminum content, which is rather expected because of multi-domain behavior of these compositions in copper cobalt ferrite. Grain growth is almost accompanied with grain size, which is increasing with copper and aluminum content. So it appears that copper and aluminum content favours the grain growth. The scanning electron micrograph was shown above.

Fig. 2.Hysteresis patterns of the samples for $\text{Cu}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-2y}\text{Al}_{2y}\text{O}_4$ ferrite system

Fig 3: Variation of coersivity, magnetic moment, Remnent magnetization and saturation magnetization with copper and aluminium content for $\text{Cu}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-2y}\text{Al}_{2y}\text{O}_4$ ferrite system

The value of n_B was observed which goes on decreasing for aluminium doped copper cobalt ferrite with increasing aluminium and copper content. Addition of Cu^{2+} content replaces Fe^{3+} from A to B site which produces canting of the magnetic spins and results in the decrease in both magnetic moments on A and B sites. This clearly indicates the decrease in A-B interaction.

Saturation magnetization is found increasing upto 20 % of copper content and thereafter decreases. The increasing trend of saturation magnetisation with Cu^{2+} content up to $x=0.2$ suggest that the Neels two sub - lattice

model is predominating up to $x = 0.2$ and thereafter Y-K three sub lattice predominant. The decrease in saturation magnetization (M_s) can also be explained in the light of Yafet-Kittle model of triangular spins.[16]

The coercivity decreases with particle size as suggested by Liu et al. The large value of coercivity essentially originates from the anisotropy of the copper ions at the octahedral (B) site due to its important spin orbit coupling. The coercive field (H_c) in Al doped copper cobalt ferrite is found to decrease with increasing Aluminum content in the doped copper cobalt

ferrites, which may be attributed to the loss of anisotropy due to the migration of Cu^{2+} ions to the tetrahedral site and also due to the decrease in the ferrous content in doped copper cobalt ferrite. The decrease in coercivity of samples is accompanied by the reduction of saturation magnetization and remnant magnetization. The reason for the decrease in coercivity of copper cobalt ferrite is the decrease in magneto-crystalline anisotropy by lowering the concentration of Fe^{2+} ions at the octahedral sites in the spinel lattice because Fe^{2+} ions are also a source of the magnetic anisotropy in ferrites.

The remnant magnetization (M_r) of Al^{3+} doped copper cobalt ferrite shows a decreasing behaviour with increase in copper and Al content from $x = 0.00$ to $x = 0.1$ and $y=0.05, 0.15, 0.25$. The decrease in M_r is due to lower magnetic moment of Al^{3+} as compared to Fe^{3+} .

Conclusion:

Copper cobalt ferrite is partially inverse spinel ferrite. Addition of Al^{3+} ions replaces Fe^{3+} on (B) site resulting in increase of lattice constant a , decrease in ionic radii (R_A) and bond length (O-A). The lattice constant obtained from XRD data shows increases. The coercivity (H_c), magnetic moment (n_B), with copper and aluminium content goes on decreasing.

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